

188.992 Assignment 2 Group 24-B

DANIEL MAZANEK, 12005060, TU Vienna, Austria

ELIAS HIRSCH, 12341086, TU Vienna, Austria

QIQI HE, 12309801, TU Vienna, Austria

SHERLYNE NDIWA, 12331442, TU Vienna, Austria

In this study, we aimed to validate the findings of gender biases in relevance judgment datasets, originally presented in a paper as part of our course "188.992 Experiment Design for Data Science" at TU Vienna. Using the authors' code, we replicated their analysis with a fine-tuned BERT model and were able to partially validate the author's results.

ACM Reference Format:

Daniel Mazanek, 12005060, Elias Hirsch, 12341086, Qiqi He, 12309801, and Sherlyne Ndiwa, 12331442. 2024. 188.992 Assignment 2 Group 24-B. In *Proceedings of (199.992 Group 24-B)*, 4 pages.

1 INTRODUCTION

In this report, we tackle the task of replicating the findings from the paper [1] as part of our coursework for "188.992 Experiment Design for Data Science" at TU Vienna. The original study brought to light the critical issue of gender biases in information retrieval systems, focusing on relevance judgment datasets. These datasets play a crucial role in evaluating information retrieval techniques and in training systems that rank information. The researchers used a fine-tuned BERT model to analyze how gender might be associated with these datasets, uncovering the presence of gender-based biases. Afterwards, the authors used the well-established Linguistic Inquiry and Word Count (LIWC) toolkit [3] to quantitatively measure various psychological characteristics.

Our goal was to validate these findings by replicating the study. With the authors' code available under <https://github.com/aminbigdeli/gender-bias-in-relevance-judgements>, we were able to directly start the replication process. However, we encountered a few challenges which took us some time, more in detail in section 3 of this report. Furthermore, as the LIWC toolkit [3] is not available as a free software and there was no option to get a free license key somewhere, we were not able to recreate their findings about stereotypical biases at all.

Our code is available under: <https://github.com/mazinator/expdes-assignment-2-group-24B.git>

2 ANALYZATION OF THE EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup consisted of 4 main steps:

- (1) Train BERT-model based on "msmarco.csv"
- (2) Predict labels for "gender_specific_wordlist.txt"
- (3) Use best performing model for the next steps
- (4) Use these predictions to measure various psychological characteristics with the help of the LIWC toolkit
- (5) Report on gender stereotypical biases

53 The setup itself as well as their workflow can be described as mostly complete and consistent. Besides the issues for
54 reproducibility mentioned in the other sections, we note that the authors did not further investigate the possibility of
55 carrying inherent biases because they are using pre-trained models.
56

57 3 REPRODUCTION

58 3.1 Data

59 The primary hurdle encountered pertained to the accessibility of datasets utilized in the original study [1]. Although
60 the repository furnished robustly documented code for training and prediction purposes, the two datasets essential to
61 the study were not provided by a link or in the repository. Hence, we needed to look into the papers cited by [1]. The
62 authors of [1] used two datasets.
63
64

65 The first dataset contains queries and the annotated gender for the query, published by [4] where the dataset is
66 provided by the authors in a github repository under [https://github.com/navid-rekabsaz/GenderBias_IR/blob/master/
67 resources/queries_gender_annotated.csv](https://github.com/navid-rekabsaz/GenderBias_IR/blob/master/resources/queries_gender_annotated.csv).
68

69 The second dataset provides queries which are annotated by a model trained based on the first dataset. The authors of
70 the original study [1] referenced the article [2] in which the second dataset is introduced, called MS Marco. The authors of
71 [2] don't provide a direct download link to the dataset, but a link to the homepage [https://microsoft.github.io/msmarco/
72](https://microsoft.github.io/msmarco/) on which multiple versions of the dataset and also other datasets are published.
73
74

75 To find the correct dataset on the website <https://microsoft.github.io/msmarco/> we compared the available datasets
76 by numbers of entries, as the authors of [1] stated that they had 51,827 queries after filtering out data points from the
77 first dataset [4]. Hence, the dataset had to contain entries in that magnitude of entries. That led to the conclusion
78 that the following dataset was used by the authors of the original paper: [https://msmarco.blob.core.windows.net/
79 msmarcoranking/qrels.dev.tsv](https://msmarco.blob.core.windows.net/msmarcoranking/qrels.dev.tsv)
80

81 Also, the 'msmarco.csv' referenced in the code and used by the authors of the original study [1] is based on the
82 second dataset. However, the authors of [1] didn't provide code to replicate the 'marco.csv'. Therefore we created the
83 Notebook 'Step 1 - Data Gathering.ipynb' and could nearly replicate the specified number of 51,827 queries (one query
84 less than in the original paper). So there remains a degree of uncertainty regarding an exact match.
85

86 3.2 Software

87 Regarding the software environment, the file "requirements.txt" in the GitHub repository was very helpful as it clearly
88 listed (most of) the package versions needed to rerun the code.
89

90 However, the Python version was not specified. To address this, we referred to the release date of the paper and
91 decided to use the Python version which was released six months prior, version 3.7.5rc1. This decision was based on
92 the assumption that the authors would have used the a current version of Python available around the assumed time of
93 their research (which we assume to be 6 months before the paper was published).
94

95 We have setup a virtual environment in a Jupyter Notebook to run the Python version stated above.
96

97 Furthermore, the version of [3] is not stated in the original paper.
98

99 3.3 Code Modifications

100 The code itself was clear and solid, however adapting the code to work with the two datasets we created involved a few
101 modifications:
102
103

105 For the "msmarco.csv" file:

- 106
- 107
- 108 • The dataset was expected to have numerical values for gender, but these were not initially present in our version
- 109 • We noted that the column headers were missing, which required us to add them manually
- 110 • An index column was apparent in the dataset, which was not expected by the original code
- 111 • We encountered issues with correctly splitting the dataset due to the presence of the delimiter within the queries
- 112 themselves
- 113

114

115 For the "gender_specific_wordlist.txt" file:

- 116
- 117
- 118 • The original code anticipated this file to be in CSV format
- 119 • There was a slight discrepancy in the file name
- 120 • Similar to the "msmarco.csv" file, this dataset also lacked column headers
- 121

122

123 **3.4 Partially Missing Code**

124

125 The authors have trained 8 different classifiers; 6 of them fall into the category of "dynamic embeddings", the other 2

126 into "static embeddings".

127 The author's code provided only reproduces their best model (which is the one that they use for the analysis with the

128 LIWC toolkits. This leaves an obvious information gap, as we cannot check if the other models are indeed worse than

129 the BERT-model. Also, not all of the 8 classifiers are described enough in detail to ensure the same training as the

130 authors made.

131

132

133

134 **4 COMPARISON TO ORIGINAL PERFORMANCE**

135

136 The author's performances are stated in table 1 on page 3 of the original paper. They have examined 8 different classifiers,

137 only one of them is available in their code. They have reached an accuracy of 0.856. We were able to reach an accuracy

138 of 0.838 on average. Therefore, with a slight deviation, we can confirm their accuracy for this classifier.

139

140

141

142 **5 ANALYZING STEREOTYPICAL BIASES**

143

143 Due to the fact that the LIWC-toolkit requires a license for 30 dollars and that we were not able to get a free license

144 somehow, we were not able to reproduce the last two steps of their process.

145

146

147

148 **6 SUMMARY**

149

149 We were able to partially reproduce the author's results and, for that part, we can confirm their outcomes.

150 We can confirm that the authors experiment setup and workflow is mostly fine as mentioned in section 2.

151 Unfortunately, due to the partially missing code described in section 3.4 and the absence of a free license for the LIWC

152 toolkit, we are not able to fully recreate the paper and confirm their findings regarding stereotypical biases in relevance

153 judgement documents.

154

155

156

A EXAMINATION OF POSSIBLE PROBLEMS

Problem	Encountered
Code not provided	No
Code partially not provided	Yes, see section 3.4
Faulty code provided	Partially faulty from our perspective because data was not provided and (maybe) therefore some preprocessing was needed, see section 3.3
Software versions missing	Python and LIWC version missing
Specific hardware/software setup	Regarding software, setting up a virtual environment for the older python version was necessary
Data not provided	Yes, see section 3.1
Data partially not provided	See section 3.1
Metadata not provided	No
Metrics/baselines not discussed	No
Experimental setup not described	No
Experiment workflow incomplete	No
Inconsistencies in paper/code/data	No
Results differ significantly	Not for the part that we were able to recreate

REFERENCES

- [1] Morteza Zihayat Amin Bigdeli, Negar Arabzadeh and Ebrahim Bagheri. 2021. Exploring Gender Biases in Information Retrieval Relevance Judgement Datasets. *Springer Nature Switzerland* (2021), 9. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-72240-1_18
- [2] Tri Nguyen, Mir Rosenberg, Xia Song, Jianfeng Gao, Saurabh Tiwary, Rangan Majumder, and Li Deng. 2016. MS MARCO: A human generated machine reading comprehension dataset. *choice* 2640 (2016), 660.
- [3] James W Pennebaker, Martha E Francis, and Roger J Booth. 2001. Linguistic inquiry and word count: LIWC 2001. *Mahway: Lawrence Erlbaum Associates* 71, 2001 (2001), 2001.
- [4] Navid Rekabsaz and Markus Schedl. 2020. Do Neural Ranking Models Intensify Gender Bias?. In *Proceedings of the 43rd International ACM SIGIR Conference on Research and Development in Information Retrieval (Virtual Event, China) (SIGIR '20)*. Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2065–2068. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3397271.3401280>